

THE ROLE OF THE INTEGRATION OF SCIENCE, EDUCATION AND PRODUCTION IN THE TRAINING OF PERSONNEL FOR CONSTRUCTION EDUCATIONAL AREAS

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Abstract. *In this scientific article, methods for the implementation of the science taste and production integration are shown to further improve the quality of education in construction educational areas. The activities carried out by the professors and teachers of the department and their results are covered in this area.*

Keywords: *integration, Science, Education, production, qualification practice, technology, economics, graduation work, innovation, research, scientific development, material.*

РОЛЬ ИНТЕГРАЦИИ НАУКИ, ОБРАЗОВАНИЯ И ПРОИЗВОДСТВА В ПОДГОТОВКЕ КАДРОВ ДЛЯ СТРОИТЕЛЬНЫХ ОБРАЗОВАТЕЛЬНЫХ НАПРАВЛЕНИЙ

Аннотация. *В данной научной статье показаны методы реализации вкуса науки и интеграции производства для дальнейшего повышения качества образования по строительным образовательным направлениям. В этой области освещаются деятельность, проводимая профессорами и преподавателями кафедры, и их результаты.*

Ключевые слова: *интеграция, наука, образование, производство, квалификационная практика, технология, экономика, выпускная работа, инновации, исследования, научные разработки, материал.*

INTRODUCTION

Ensuring the competitiveness of the national economy in the conditions of today's globalization, the rapid development of Science and technology through the training of highly qualified specialists with deep modern knowledge, achieve a wide introduction of innovative scientific developments into the production of new high requirements for Science, Education and business. Uzbekistan is a science-driven country. As early as the Middle Ages, The Mamun Academy was established in Khiva. The Eastern renaissance of the IX-XIV centuries made an invaluable contribution to the development of the sciences of our great ancestors - modern mathematics, trigonometry and geography Muhammad ibn Musa al-Khorezm, who founded the science of algebra al-Khorezm, the main astronomical instrument in the Middle Ages – Ahmad Fargani, who developed the theory of usturlob, was one of the first in world science to come up

with original new ideas on the theory of the seas and the creation of a spherical globe of the Earth, Abu Rayhon Beruni, who was awarded the title of one of the greatest thinkers of mankind, such as Abu Ali ibn Sina, Mirzo Ulugbek, who gained fame Their universal discoveries, the scientific schools they created led to the emergence and adulthood of a wave of new and new talented generations. This, along with the rapid growth of the economy, agriculture and urban economy, the high level of development of crafts and trade, the construction of roads, the opening of new caravan routes, also served to ensure relative stability on the kurrai-land. Taking an example from the great discoveries of the geniuses of the East, the ancestors of the people of Science Of The Present Time, re-perceiving and evaluating the laws that have arisen over the centuries, carry out large-scale deep scientific research to increase the power of independent states, form and develop the modern economy.

RESEARCH MATERIALS AND METHODOLOGY

At present, the integration of Science Education and production has become one of the important factors in raising the quality of education to a higher level. There are several factors in the training of personnel in the areas of construction education, including in the educational direction "production of building materials, objects and structures:

- raising qualification practice to a qualitatively new level
- conducting some classes in specialty subjects at production enterprises;
- more coverage of students for participation in research work carried out by professors and teachers of the Department on the basis of an economic contract;
- attracting leading specialists of production enterprises to train students;
- wider involvement of high-level students in scientific seminars under the Department of specialty and ensuring their participation in lectures.

A comprehensive approach to the above-mentioned activities will serve as an important element in further improving the quality of Education. In subsequent years, many activities were carried out in the implementation of the integration of Science Education and production by professors and teachers of the Department of building materials and products. In particular, special attention was paid to conducting qualification practice for students of each stage. As a leader of the practice, leading professors and teachers of the department, as well as experienced specialists of production enterprises were appointed. Each student was provided with a perfectly developed methodological instruction in accordance with the type of practice. The methodological instruction was given the topic of independent work devoted to thinking as well as conducting small studies. At the end of the internship, students' reports were listened with the participation of specialists from the production enterprise. As a result, the efficiency achieved at the end of the qualification practice has reached a new level. The department has branches in "techno standard test" LLC and "Bunyodkor-3" LLC, and laboratory classes on "building materials and products", practical classes on "technology of concrete fillers", "technology of concrete and reinforced concrete products" are held at these branches.

RESEARCH RESULTS

At the department there is a scientific seminar on building materials and structures, professors, undergraduates and talented students regularly participate in the seminar. Engineering and technical staff of production enterprises in this field also participate in the Seminar with their lectures. Activities aimed at improving the quality of Education give its

positive result. In particular, over the next three years, 19 students who graduated from The Bachelor's degree in this direction of Education studied at the master's level.

CONCLUSION

Of these, 9 are studying at the Tashkent architectural and Construction Institute, 2 at prestigious universities in China, 1 at the University of the Russian Federation, and 8 at the Namangan Engineering Construction Institute in various master's specialties. Currently, professors and teachers of the department are the South Ural State University of the Russian Federation, Novosibirsk State University of architecture and construction, M. On the basis of a cooperation agreement with the University of South Kazakhstan named after Auezov, they are establishing joint training of personnel.

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